

ORIGINAL PAPER

An evaluation of *Coffea cruda* effect on rats

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To investigate the effect of the homeopathic medicine *Coffea cruda* on sleep pattern, it was orally administered to rats at the beginning of their waking period. EEG from the parietal region was recorded during their next sleep cycle. Applying an FFT algorithm, spectral in the δ band, 0.5–2.5 Hz, was chosen as a marker parameter, evaluated for control and verum groups using a double-blind protocol. Power in the verum group was statistically higher than baseline value, it was not statistically different in the control group. The results indicate that an enhancement in EEG slow delta activity is associated with *Coffea cruda*. British Homeopathic Journal (2000) 89, 122–126.

Keywords: *Coffea cruda*; sleep homeostasis; sleep deprivation; NREM intensity

Introduction

Sleep disorders involve symptoms which may be relevant for choosing the right medicine in homeopathic diagnosis. Such signs (with their modalities) can be found in the Materia Medica related to different medicaments. *Coffea cruda* is one of the main remedies in this field. Moreover, since *Coffea cruda* was incorporated into homeopathic practice in 1823 by Dr Stapf,¹ insomnia has been identified as one of its foremost symptoms.

Insomnia is also related to coffee drinking, specifically to caffeine, which is one of the main components of *Coffea cruda*'s mother tincture. Its sleep inhibiting action modifies sleep homeostasis. Variations in sleep pattern due to caffeine administration have been assessed through different approaches, two of which are as follows.

The first procedure, carried out on humans, involves buildup of a homeostatic sleep drive attenuation because of caffeine intake in the morning,² with diminishing NREM (non-rapid eye movement) activity as the corresponding outcome due to a still unknown mechanism. The second involves sleep deprivation in rats from intraperitoneal caffeine administration at sleep onset, and implies an increase in sleep intensity. As a result, an enhancement in slow-wave activity in NREM stage is detected by

specific mathematical analysis.³ In both cases, the effect of caffeine can be estimated through a common parameter, NREM sleep intensity, evaluated as slow-wave activity, whose accepted definition is the spectral power in the δ (delta) band.⁴ It is expected that *Coffea cruda* will bring about a similar outcome in healthy subjects under analogous circumstances.

Our group has published several results on the physicochemical characterization of the homeopathic effect.^{5–7} The main purpose of this study is the identification and measurement of a parameter whose variation could be associated and interpreted in agreement with the well known effect of *Coffea cruda*, in an attempt to provide a common terminology to improve communication between homeopathy and other branches of science. In order to reach this objective, NREM activity changes produced by *Coffea cruda* administered during the waking period were measured in rats.

It is accepted that prescribing in homeopathy is complex;⁸ diverse symptoms are taken into account to choose the right medicine. Despite this complexity, a specific sign of particular relevance (or 'keynote') can be identified for most medicines.⁹ In some cases this main symptom is associated with sleep alteration. However, such sleep disturbances are of a distinct, qualitatively different, nature; differences include hours of waking during the night, duration of sleeplessness, quality of sleep (peaceful, restful, disturbed, etc.) and dreams. However, those features in some cases could be difficult to remember accurately, hence the relevance of trying to identify a specific and measurable change in the EEG (electroencephalogram) with a particular homeopathic medicine.

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Materials and methods

Subjects

Subjects were 30 young adult male Wistar rats weighing 250–350 g. Three 1.5 mm diameter stainless steel electrodes were implanted in the animals' cranium skull. The electrodes were set on the surface cerebral cortex by means of trepanation, securing them with dental resin, so they could be wired to a multichannel amplifier. Before trepanation, each rat was intraperitoneally anaesthetized with 40 mg/kg of pentobarbital sodium. Two electrodes were implanted bilaterally in the parietal region, one in the frontal area for reference (ground). Trepanation points correspond to the following stereotaxic coordinates: 3.8 mm posterior to Bregma and 4.5 mm lateral to the side of the central line for the bilateral electrodes. After a 6-day recovery from the surgical procedure, a further day light habituation period was allowed with the electrodes connected to a signal amplifier by a cable that allowed the animal freedom of movement. The next day measurements started. The animals were fed normal rat diet and drinking water *ad libitum*. Control and verum groups were formed.

Animal welfare

In our handling of rats in this and related experiments, we observe several rules that help ameliorate their physiological shock even further than required by Mexican Federal Regulations, the PROY-NOM-062-200-1999 protocol:

- (i) The electrodes do not penetrate the meninges, so strictly speaking there is no invasion of brain tissue.
- (ii) In about two weeks rats expel the electrodes due to cranial regeneration; they fully recover from the surgical intervention and lead a normal life after the experiment.
- (iii) Measurements took place during the animals' sleep period.

Set-up

Rats were housed individually in two wooden cages with a glass peephole window to allow observation. 50 cm³ free volume cages were built to avoid external stimuli and provide illumination. Temperature was maintained constant at the rats thermoneutral temperature,¹⁰ 29 ± 0.5°C, in order to prevent sleep pattern modifications due to hypothermia.³

Each subject was connected to a P511 Grass pre-amplifier module, its controls set as follows: amplification factor 20,000, band-pass filter 0.3–35 Hz, line filter on. The output was sampled at 5 Hz and online digitized with a National Instruments AT-MIO-16XE-50 card; the outcoming numerical register was stored in a computer for mathematical analysis. Sample frequency was chosen taking into

account the following considerations. Firstly, waves between 0.5–4 Hz (δ band) compound NREM stage,¹¹ in which waves of 2 Hz or slower and amplitudes greater than 75 μ V constitute 20–50% or even more¹² of such an interval. In addition, the Nyquist theorem states that the sampling frequency should be at least twice the highest frequency processed. Because the entire session recording was analysed at the same time and data management became slow as file size increased, the 5 Hz sampling frequency was selected. This sampling rate assures that features up to 2.5 Hz are gathered and a complete 7-hour register, once digitized, turned out a time series with 127,000 voltage inputs. As a consequence, computational time could be kept within reasonable limits.

Experimental procedure

The experimental method consisted in allocating two rats, one to a cage, after they had concluded the preparation detailed above and connecting them to the amplifier. All records were carried out through a 7-hour sleep period of the animals (10:00–17:00). All tests were performed using a double-blind protocol as follows.

First day

The day after the conditioning stage, the first recording session started. The rats were fed their regular diet and allowed purified water without any medicament. The computer file from this day constituted the 'baseline' signal. At the end of this step, at around 17:00, one of the animals was given 0.5 ml of *Coffea cruda* obtained from Laboratorios Medicor S.A. de C.V., 30c, dissolved in 200 ml of drinking water in the feeding bottle. The second rat was given the same quantity of drinking water only. The person in charge of this assignment did not know the identity of the substance being given to each rat.

Second day

The quantity of consumed liquid was noted and a second data gathering period commenced at the same time as the previous day. At the end of this trial set, this experiment concluded and the process was repeated with two new subjects, until all 30 were tested. Mathematical analysis of the data was carried out by someone blind to the source of the file. No liquid intake was allowed during the recording time, that is 10:00–17:00 during both sessions.

Mathematical analysis

Before any mathematical operation, the record was visually examined and noisy segments due to disconnections or external artifacts (eg scratching) were eliminated in such a way that records related to the two subjects in each trial set were exactly the same size and representing the same period for both days (Figure 1).

Figure 1 A representative digitized register from the EEG of a sleeping rat. Differences in amplitudes reflecting sleep stage voltage changes of sleep periods involved are shown. This record has 9000 points and represents the digitized data from half an hour of experimentation at 5 Hz.

A band-pass filter with low and high cutoff frequencies (0.5 and 2.5 Hz respectively) was applied in order to eliminate the frequencies outside this band. The filtered data was subjected to a Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) algorithm and the 0.5–2.5 Hz band power was computed for such file according to the periodogram method.¹³

The purpose of this analysis was to assess sleep intensity by evaluating NREM activity by EEG, power in the 0.5–2.5 Hz band. This domain constitutes the main NREM frequency component.¹² Thus, in this research NREM activity as a marker of sleep intensity was estimated as spectral power in the 0.5–2.5 Hz band evaluated in the complete noise-free file. The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated from volume of consumed liquid and the variation between administration and baseline for control and verum groups.

Results

Results are shown in Tables 1 and 2, and Figure 2. Table 1 shows results for the control group: the first column corresponds to trial set number. EEG power for the first (baseline value) and second (water) days are shown in the second and third column. Percentage variation between administration and baseline is listed in column 4. Volume of consumed liquid, in millilitres is listed in column 5. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between columns 4 and 5 is $r = 0.2$, with $P = 0.47$, which implies that there is no linear relationship.

Results from the verum group are summarized in Table 2 in the same way. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between columns 4 and 5 is $r = 0.34$, with $P = 0.22$, which shows that there is no linear relationship between them.

A t -test for dependent samples performed between columns 2 (baseline) and 3 (drinking water)

Table 1 Power in 0.5–2.5 Hz band of filtered EEG for control group. Column 1 displays the trial set number in sequential order. Columns 2 and 3 show power in 0.5–2.5 Hz interval days of first (baseline) and second (administration) days, with drinking water intake in both cases. The difference between them is not statistically significant ($P = 0.48$). The variation as a percentage between columns 2 and 3 is given in column 4. Column 5 lists the volume of liquid consumed

Trial set	Baseline (a)	Water (b)	(b-a)/a	Volume
1	20147	18856	- 6.41	50
2	4561	6313	+38.41	60
3	22849	23935	+ 4.75	52
4	16680	25922	+55.41	43
5	11504	9422	- 18.09	38
6	29864	10832	- 63.73	40
7	15780	17868	+ 13.23	0
8	14913	16987	+ 13.91	65
9	17797	18416	+ 3.48	61
10	24204	23936	- 1.11	48
11	22735	18430	- 18.94	42
12	28296	24658	- 12.86	0
13	34530	35071	+ 1.57	40
14	23911	16656	- 30.34	43
15	17206	20243	+ 17.65	56

in Table 1 does not exhibit a significant change ($P = 0.48$), whereas the same test carried out between the same columns in Table 2, ie baseline vs *Coffea cruda*, shows a significant change ($P = 0.02$).

Figure 2a displays column 4 in Table 1, the variation of the power in the 0.5–2.5 Hz band for the control group. The variation is consistent with zero ($P = 0.49$). In Figure 2b the same data for the verum group is shown: the percentage variation between *Coffea cruda* vs baseline. The variation is significantly greater than zero ($P = 0.01$).

We conclude that *Coffea cruda* 30c brought forth a significant after-effect in respect of the baseline value.

Table 2 Power in 0.5–2.5 Hz band of filtered EEG for verum group. Trial set number is listed in column 1. Power in 0.5–2.5 Hz interval data from baseline and verum sessions is shown in columns 2 and 3 respectively. Both data groups are statistically different ($P=0.02$). Variation as a percentage of verum vs baseline is displayed in column 4. Column 5 shows the volume of liquid consumed

Trial set	Baseline(a)	Verum(b)	(b-a)/a	Volume
16177	14509		- 10.32	40
6456	6778		+ 5.00	52
16297	21714		+ 33.24	46
12956	13512		+ 4.30	50
23697	23275		- 1.78	40
17944	20716		+ 15.45	45
22216	25168		+ 13.29	60
22490	22939		+ 2.00	55
15620	18172		+ 16.34	45
7306	7421		+ 1.58	43
11603	16354		+ 40.95	55
20928	25834		+ 23.44	60
24244	23807		- 1.80	40
12010	16066		+ 33.77	47
16613	14660		- 11.75	52

Discussion

According to these findings, an enhancement in slow delta activity is associated with *Coffea cruda*. The question arises whether *Coffea cruda*'s effect is (1) due to its capacity to provoke insomnia, (2) because of its analgesic properties, or (3) the mixed effect of (1) and (2).

1. The Materia Medica states that one of the main signs associated with *Coffea cruda* activity is insomnia. According to the similia principle, this symptom will be generated in healthy subjects, which implies sleep deprivation. The diminishing of NREM power is one of the main sleep pattern features that characterizes this condition.¹⁴ Because healthy subjects were chosen for the experiment and the results show an enhancement of NREM power, they contrast with the expected outcome.

However, previous studies have revealed that sleep loss provokes a compensatory reaction which consists

Figure 2 (a) Variation in power 0.5–2.5 Hz band for control group between the first (baseline) and second session (water) expressed as percentage change (see column 4 in Table 1). Errors bars display the statistical error. This quantity is not statistically different from zero ($P=0.49$). (b) Percentage of change of the same parameter as in (a) for verum group, between baseline and verum, when *Coffea cruda* 30c was administered to the experimental subjects (see column 4 in Table 2). This magnitude is significantly greater than zero ($P=0.01$).

of an increase of sleep intensity in order to maintain constant the mean level of sleep. This is known as 'sleep homeostasis'.¹⁵ The main indicator of the intensity of NREM sleep is slow-wave activity, identified with slow-wave power in delta band. This marker augments after sleep deprivation with a maximum in the 2.25–2.5 Hz interval, declining as the time of sleep goes by.¹⁶ A possible interpretation of the results could be as follows. Because as long as approximately 17 h elapsed between the animals commencing intake and the second gathering session at 10:00 the following day, it may be that the second record was gathered during the insomnia-recovery stage.

The results appear to reflect the effect of sleep homeostasis against sleep loss. According to Hahnemann¹⁷ such sleep loss could be related to the primary action of medicines, whereas NREM intensity enhancement could be identified as the organism's counteraction, ie the secondary action.

2. It is worthwhile considering the cranial lesion due to trepanation for electrode implantation. In fact, the incidence of headache as a post-traumatic symptom¹⁸ has been reported, as well as the appearance of waves at 2.5 Hz as a result of cranioencephalic trauma.¹⁹ It is said that *Coffea cruda* is one of the most powerful homeopathic analgesic agents, a splitting headache being a specific sign. Vijnovsky⁹ describes such pain as 'if a nail were stuck in the parietal zone'. It is possible that this homeopathic medicine should have some effect enhancing the activity of 2.5 Hz waves, resembling perhaps Hanhemann's postulate that the curative capacities of medicaments reside in developing a very similar but stronger artificial disease.¹⁷

3. Because the experiment was carried out during the sleep period and the homeopathic stimuli affect living beings as a whole,¹⁷ it could be that the enhancement in 0.5–2.5 Hz band represents a superimposed mixture of (1) and (2). Interactions between host defense and sleep has been recently identified from animal investigations, specifically the immunosupportive function of NREM sleep with an increase in EEG delta activity as a result.²⁰ Such systemic action could be reflected in host defence activation. The fact that these two main signs (insomnia and headache) relate to *Coffea cruda* and are associated with the same 2.5 Hz average wave activity is concordant with the holism of the homeopathic medicine, that is, one single medicine might cure two (or more) symptoms, apparently not connected.

These hypotheses bring to the surface important issues related to the mechanism of action of homeopathic medicines (time effect, a parameter comparable to elimination rate, receptors, etc..) which are beyond the scope of this study. Additional investigations are required to address these matters; the research area is open and the parameter we have identified could be a tool for further investigation.

In conclusion, we are far from a complete interpretation. The relevance of this study resides in

the identification of a physicochemical parameter related to *Coffea cruda*, whose variation is in systematic and objective way despite variable biological sensitivity.

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